

AI-Based Enhancement of 4D Flow MRI for Hemodynamic Assessment in Bicuspid Aortic Valve

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Abstract. Four-dimensional Flow MRI (4D Flow MRI) is a powerful modality for visualizing cardiovascular blood flow in space and time, enabling detailed assessment of flow patterns and hemodynamics [1]. However, its clinical adoption is limited due to complex data analysis and long processing times that exceed what is practical in routine workflows [2,3]. These challenges are especially critical in patients with Bicuspid Aortic Valve (BAV), where subtle flow abnormalities must be captured for accurate risk stratification.

To address these limitations, we introduce a unified, AI-powered post-processing framework tailored for clinical 4D Flow MRI in BAV patients. Our method performs end-to-end denoising, aliasing correction, and artifact removal, while also achieving two-fold super-resolution—enabling sharper vessel boundaries and improved visibility of fine-grained flow features. The architecture extends 4DFlowNet [4], a convolutional neural network originally designed for synthetic data, by integrating domain-specific loss functions and data augmentation strategies to optimize performance on real-world clinical scans.

Specifically, we trained the 4DFlowNet network using a patch-based strategy ($16 \times 16 \times 16$ voxels), incorporating over 36,000 velocity patches extracted from 70 BAV patients with 30 time frames each. To improve clinical relevance, we introduced a perceptual loss to enhance structural consistency of flow, and an eddy current loss to penalize low-frequency phase distortions commonly caused by gradient-induced eddy currents in MRI. Training was conducted over 100+ epochs with an initial learning rate of 0.0002, which was gradually reduced during fine-tuning.

The same architecture was reused for super-resolution by simulating low-resolution inputs: we transformed the complex velocity data into the frequency domain (k-space), cropped the central low-frequency components to remove fine spatial details, added Gaussian noise, and then transformed the data back into the image domain. The network was then trained to reconstruct the original high-resolution velocity fields.

We validated performance against expert-labeled ground truth. Quantitative results demonstrate consistent improvements over baseline models in PSNR, SSIM, RMSE, and Bland-Altman agreement. As shown in Figures 1 and 2, the model achieves clearer vessel depiction and better preservation of flow features. This work advances post-processing of 4D Flow MRI toward automated, real-

time integration in clinical pipelines, supporting more precise and accessible cardiovascular diagnostics.

Keywords: AI-based Post-Processing, 4D Flow MRI Super-Resolution, Hemodynamic Modeling in BAV.

Figure. 1. Side-by-side comparison showing results from standard manual preprocessing (left), original 4DFlowNet model (center), and modified 4DFlowNet (right). The modified model demonstrates improved noise reduction and structural accuracy in capturing flow dynamics.

Figure. 2. Illustrating the enhancement from original low-resolution data (left) to raw data (DICOM)-quality (center) and super-resolution output (right), showcasing improved clarity and detail capture with the modified 4DFlowNet model.

References

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